

PRIME PETE

PRIMARY EDUCATION PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHER EDUCATION

Modular Primary PETE programme consisting of course modules and micro- modules

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Technical sheet

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Website: <https://www.primepete.com/>

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1. Introduction

The aim of the PRIME PETE Erasmus+ project is to develop a primary PETE programme that can be implemented by any Higher Education Institution (HEI) in Europe, cognisant of the diverse settings for teaching primary Physical Education (PE) in the different countries and jurisdictions. A primary Physical Education Teacher Education (PETE) programme (Intellectual Output 5, IO#5) informed by IO#1, IO#2, IO#3 and IO#4, can help raise the quality of PETE and subsequently the quality of PE at primary school level in Europe.

The PRIME PETE programme is a modular programme consisting of course modules and micro-modules (discussed below) based on the theoretical and methodological framework for primary PETE (IO#4) and is available for download on an open online course platform (IO#9) under a respective license. The content was developed in the English language. Some module and micro-modules are complemented by illustrative resources and support materials.

The target groups addressed by the PRIME PETE programme are:

- teacher education institutions
- educators
- teacher associations, subject (physical education) associations, sports organisations
- stakeholders including policy makers with responsibility for primary teacher education.

A glossary of the terms used in this IO#5 report can be viewed in Appendix 1.

The PRIME PETE programme is innovative as it is the first online European programme for primary teachers available with a focus on PE. Thus, this programme should allow interested HEI and teacher education institutions who are currently offering primary PETE programmes or those who are developing programmes to choose appropriate modules for flexible use and implementation. Due to the availability of PRIME PETE modules and micro-modules that are ready for implementation by the project partners and other stakeholders, expected impact and transferability potential includes sharing of the modules to facilitate engagement in student and teacher mobility, as one major objective beyond the project lifetime.

The methodology used to design and develop this aspect of the PRIME PETE programme consisted of the project partners developing the course modules and micro-modules. A PRIME PETE module is a distinct, discrete, self-contained element of the PRIME PETE programme. It represents a formally structured

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learning experience with a coherent and explicit set of learning outcomes, expressed in terms of competences to be gained. A PRIME PETE micro-module is a part/fraction of a module to help students have a specific understanding of a particular topic in a module.

The modules and micro-modules are informed by partners' experience within their institutions, the literature review and the Delphi Study (IO#1) and the recommendations on primary PETE (IO#2). The work was further informed by the Primary PE Teacher Profile (PPETP) (IO#3) developed for both generalist and specialist primary teachers, whose responsibility is to teach children PE in primary schools.

To contextualise the PRIME PETE modules and micro-modules to university settings, the PRIME PETE programme:

- a) proposes that the identity, characteristics and competences of the student teacher are considered for delivering quality physical education (QPE)(IO#3)
- b) acknowledges that modules (e.g., psychology, sociology, philosophy) for the integration of PE in the multidisciplinary educational PETE process complement the work described in the PRIME PETE programme. However, these multidisciplinary modules do not form part of the PRIME PETE programme (IO#4)
- c) recommends an allocation of 240/300 ECTS for study of PE over 4-5 years (IO#4)
- d) recommends a minimum compulsory allocation of ECTS for specific focus on PE for both core and extended PETE (IO#2: LTT 1*, IO#4)
- e) recommends that 20% of professional/school placement time be allocated to teaching of PE (IO#4)
- f) recommends that tutors, with specific expertise in PE, mentor students on professional/school placement (IO#2: LTT 1*)
- g) proposes that the modules of the PRIME PETE programme are underpinned by student teacher wellbeing (IO#3) and *the PRIME PETE Vision for Student Teacher Health and Wellbeing* (IO#5)

* Note the LTT 1 refers to the Learning Teaching and Training Event (partner presentations) Lisbon, February 2021

It is important to keep in mind **the PRIME PETE mission** (IO#4)

...to prepare student teachers at undergraduate level for a successful future as PE educators who build communities of competent and knowledgeable children on their physical literacy journey who value an active and healthy lifestyle and pursue physical activity. The primary PE teacher (generalist or specialist)

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is seen as a competent professional who is concerned to become more effective in assisting and enabling children's physical, social and cognitive learning and development within a variety of contexts through analysing, exploring and reflecting upon their practice.

Cognisant of the PRIME PETE mission, the development of the PRIME PETE modules and micro-modules involved six stages: (1) the design of a module and micro-module template (2) the development of module exemplars (3) the development of micro-module exemplars (4) the development of overarching elements (5) the development of the PRIME PETE Vision for Student Health and Wellbeing (6) finalising the PRIME PETE modules and micro-modules.

2. The design of a module and micro-module template

From the PRIME PETE LTT 1 Lisbon, February 2021 (online) event it was clear that all project partners used a modular system in their university programmes linked to the European Credit Transfers system (ECTS). The partners agreed to adopt this approach for the development of the PRIME PETE modules. ECTS are based on the workload students typically need to complete the required learning activities (such as lectures, seminars, projects, practical work, self-study and examinations) to achieve the expected learning outcomes. It is the common credit system in place at universities in Europe to assign credits to a programme or module and it is important to note that not all learning hours are hours spent in class sessions. (Note: one ECT credit is equivalent to 25-30 hours of a typical student's work; thus a 5-credit module comprises 125 hours of work. The exact number of hours can vary a little from country to country).

In developing a PRIME PETE module template, PE module descriptors from the universities of the project partners were discussed and analysed with a particular focus on comparing the module templates. Following partner discussion, the mission of some headings (e.g., assessments, staff, semester) was agreed. These headings were considered as bespoke to each university although a suite of assessment options, for example, is suggested in IO#4. A draft template was reviewed by partners. Building on the work undertaken in IO#1 and IO#2, two additional rows 'Dimensions Core' and 'Dimensions Extended', were added to the template. These will be discussed later. The final PRIME PETE template can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1: PRIME PETE Module and Micro-Module template

MODULE/MICRO-MODULE DETAILS	
Micro-module Title	
Suggested Number of ECTS	
Dimensions Core	
Dimensions Extended	
Setting (Online, Hybrid, Offline, Movement Based, Theory Based (Lecture or Seminar))	
Short Description	

MODULE/ MICRO-MODULE LEARNING OUTCOMES	
Upon successful completion of this module, the student will be able to:	
LO1	
LO2	
LO3	
LO4	
LO5	
LO6	

Indicative Content (list topics to be covered)

TEACHING METHODOLOGIES	
Teaching Methodologies	

FACILITIES: INDOORS AND/OR OUTDOOR

MODULE/MICRO-MODULE WORKLOAD		
Type	Learning Outcomes	Total Hours
Lecture		
Seminar/Workshop/Tutorial		
Structured Independent Work		
Independent Work		
Total Workload		

READING
Essential Reading

	RESOURCES for MODULES/SUPPORT MATERIALS for MICRO-MODULES (Expansion of Indicative Content)
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3. The development of module exemplars

Partners presented exemplars of modules across a range of themes from their University Physical Education programmes as a starting point to develop the PRIME PETE programme. An online resource, “Historica Canada Education Portal” was used as a reference point to guide further module development. Partners’ modules were analysed and amended before recording them in the PRIME PETE module template. This process resulted in the development of the first seven PRIME PETE modules (see Table 2), including some illustrative resources and support materials.

Table 2: First seven PRIME PETE modules

Planning and Implementation of Physical Education
Active School Models
Understanding Physical Education
Foundations of Primary Physical Education
Didactics of Physical Education
School Physical and Health Education
Teaching Physical Education

4. The development of micro-module exemplars

The working definition of a micro-module was agreed by partners. As defined in the introduction above, it is a part/fraction of a module to help students have a specific understanding of a particular topic in a module. Micro-modules were developed to illustrate how module content could be broken down further and these could be used by universities as ‘bite sized’ pieces of work.

Partners identified topics from their PRIME PETE modules to develop PRIME PETE micro-modules (using the same template). Seven micro-modules with some illustrative support materials were presented at the LTT 2 Brixen, Italy June 2022 (face to face) event. The agenda for the event is included in Appendix 2. Some key information about the micro-modules delivered and evaluated is presented in Table 3. The evaluation tool is described in IO#6 while the evaluation of the event is reported in IO#7. The seven micro-modules became part of the PRIME PETE programme.

5. The development of overarching elements

Self-reflection as a recommendation linked to earlier work (IO#2, IO#4) was practised in the LTT 2, as the participants were asked to record their reflections in a reflective diary. This informed the development of an overarching element (OE), *the Teacher as a Reflective Practitioner in Physical Education* (not a module or micro-module) of the PRIME PETE programme. An OE in the PRIME PETE programme can constitute a module, a piece of work, a practice or a process that may be woven into many modules and micro-modules. Two further OE emerged for the PRIME PETE programme: *Research in Physical Education* and *Professional Placement in Physical Education*. These OEs will be discussed further below.

Table 3: Micro-modules implemented at the LTT 2 Brixen, Italy 13th-17th June 2022

Partner	Title	Total Hours	Theory Based Hours	Movement Based Hours
DCU	Understanding Physical Education: Creative Dance	2	Woven in	2
FMH/UL	Teaching Physical Education: Classroom Management	3	1	2
DCU	Understanding Physical Education: Cooperative Challenges Outdoors	2	Woven in	2
Uni Bolzano	Foundations of Primary Physical Education: Values-based Education through Sport and Physical Education	3	2	1
Uni Lux	Planning and Implementation of Physical Education: Child-appropriate Physical Education	3	1 +1 student group independent work	1
Uni Seville	Didactics of Physical Education: Communication and Interaction	2	1	1
Uni Trnava	School Physical and Health Education: Inclusive Primary Physical Education	2	1	1

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Following the initial development and implementation of the micro-modules as described above, and to design the programme for the LTT 3 held in Lisbon 12th-16th September 2022 (face-to-face), the project partners grappled with progressing the work. The results of the Delphi Study (IO#1), the development of the Primary Education Physical Education Teacher Profile (PPETP) (IO#3), the recommendations arising from IO#4 and the evaluations from the LTT 2 Brixen, reported in IO#6 and IO#7 sparked much debate between the project partners. Many aspects of the programme development were considered in preparation for the LTT 3, Lisbon. The micro-modules from the LTT 2 Brixen were mapped to the dimensions and statements (IO#1 and IO#3) (see Table 4) using a coding process (Appendix 3 illustrates the outcome of this coding process) to ascertain if the programme was beginning to meet the early descriptions of the teacher profile.

There was a renewed focus on self-reflection and the use of a reflective diary by student participants, on student delivery of aspects of micro-modules, as well as on developing further knowledge and skills related to the PRIME PETE themes (IO#4). Additional micro-modules with some illustrative support materials were developed that focussed on the development of fundamental movement skills, physical literacy, inclusion, Universal Design for Learning, and digital learning. Table 5 illustrates the six additional PRIME PETE micro-modules presented at the LTT Lisbon. One further additional micro-module was prepared but not delivered, totalling 7 micro-modules. In relation to digital learning, ethical guidelines related to the use of personal iPhones in the PRIME PETE LTT events were developed and shared with the student teacher participants. These are included in Appendix 4 while the agenda for the LTT 3 Lisbon is included in Appendix 5.

Table 4: Five Dimensions and Thirteen Statements (IO#1: Delphi Study; IO#3)

Dimension 1: Knowledge development and management (D1)

- Advanced knowledge and understanding of the development of fundamental movement skills.
- Knowledge about children's overall development
- Knowledge of physical activity recommendations for children and young people

Dimension 2: Teaching, Learning and Assessment (D 2)

- Ability to plan and teach quality physical education lessons.
- Ability to provide a positive and safe learning environment.
- Ability to plan long-term and short-term physical education programmes based on students' developmental level and readiness.

Dimension 3: Learner empowerment, potential, diversity and creativity (D 3)

- Capacity and commitment to support the learning and development of all students regardless of their ability levels.
- Capacity and commitment to motivate, inspire learners and support their empowerment.
- Capacity and commitment to create situations and climates in which learners increase their self-esteem and confidence.

Dimension 4: Values, social leadership and communication (D 4)

- Capacity and commitment to the healthy development of primary school students Capacity and commitment to adhere to children's rights.
- Ability to communicate effectively both verbally and non-verbally.
- Ability to promote ethical behaviour in learners and foster a culture of valuing diversity within the classroom setting.

Dimension 5: Development as reflective professionals and life-long learners (D 5)

- Capacity and commitment to actively advocate for physical education in the school and beyond.

Table 5: Micro-Modules implemented at the LTT 3 Lisbon 12th-16th September 2022 *

Partner	Title	Total Hours	Theory Based Hours	Movement Based Hours
DCU	Understanding Physical Education: Promoting Fundamental Movement Skills	2	0	2
FMH/UL	Teaching Physical Education: Motor Development, Learning and Implications for Teaching	3	1	2
Uni Bolzano	Foundations of Physical Education: Motivation, Motivational Climate and Enjoyment in Physical Education	3	1.5	1.5
Uni Lux	Active School Models: Active School	1.5	.5	1
Uni Seville	Didactics of Physical Education: Organization and Classroom Management	2	1	1
Uni Trnava	School Physical Education and Health Education: Swimming as a Tool to Support Lifelong Physical Activity.	2	1	1

*Foundations of Physical Education: Knowledge and Understanding of Physical Activity Recommendations micro module although developed was not delivered at the LTT 3, Lisbon due to time constraints.

6. The development of a PRIME PETE Vision for Student Teacher Health and Wellbeing

The theme of student teacher wellbeing featured prominently in the PRIME PETE theoretical and methodological framework (IO#4). At both LTT 2 and LTT 3 events time was allocated for group work tasks and events with a focus on meaningful engagement of students in physical activity. For example, mid-way through both LTT programmes a day was allocated for hiking (by students and educators) prompting both social interaction between participants and physical activity. Both events were undertaken in wonderfully scenic locations maximising the inherent value of the natural environment. In response to this important aspect of the PRIME PETE agenda at the LTT events, as well as identification of a need to incorporate this important aspect i.e., student wellbeing, into the PRIME PETE programme, a student wellbeing vision

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statement was developed: a *PRIME PETE Vision for Student Teacher Health and Wellbeing* (see Table 6). This underpins the PRIME PETE programme. It was developed during IO#5 linking back to the Mission (IO#4) and project expert discussions (LTT 1, February 2021). It aspires to having health and wellbeing central to the student experience.

Table 6: PRIME PETE Vision for Student Teacher Health and Wellbeing

Note: Table 6 is continued on the next page

PRIME PETE Vision for Student Teacher Health and Wellbeing
<p>The mission of PRIME PETE is to prepare student teachers (<i>generalists or specialists</i>) as competent, analytically reflective, professionally effective professionals who are cognisant of personal health and wellbeing as they teach primary physical education.</p> <p>Student teachers contribute to building communities of competent and knowledgeable children on their physical literacy journey, who value an active and healthy lifestyle and pursue physical activity. They assist and enable children’s physical, social and cognitive learning and development within a variety of contexts underpinned by analysing, exploring and reflecting on their practice. They are role models for the children they teach. They are professional in the way they present themselves to children and to colleagues. They have positive levels of self-esteem and value their personal health and wellbeing, always striving to enhance it. PRIME PETE strives to promote the ideal of life-long health through encouraging student teachers to meet the physical activity guidelines for adults, to engage in cultural activities and to eat well and live healthily to support their undergraduate and post-graduate studies, their personal lives and professional lives as teachers.</p> <p>The PRIME PETE programme presented as a European exemplar, aspires to having health and wellbeing at its core. Through the pedagogy and content embedded in the programme it encourages collaboration, empowerment of individual responsibility, promotion of healthy lifestyle choices and development of best practice to inspire healthy behaviours.</p>

Key messages for PRIME PETE educators to underpin programmes of study for student teachers of primary physical education

- Learning how to improve the wellbeing of the student teacher and of the child is a key theme for reflection and discussion throughout modules, where creating and maintaining a positive, safe environment is central.
- Recommendations related to the learning and practice of physical activity for children are considered hand in hand with adult physical activity recommendations at the core of student teachers' professional and personal practice.
- The theory-based work to improve physical activity in primary schools considers physical education as the strategic core educational process.
- Developing motor competency is a key focus throughout all theoretical and practical work with student teachers.
- Inclusion should inform all aspects of practice in school and university environments.
- Being a participant at sporting and cultural events to promote aesthetic and cultural appreciation and enjoyment is regarded as an opportunity characterised by excitement, appreciation, respect, creativity and joy.
- Cultural choices about health are linked to the important role of teachers in influencing positive choices by children.
- Subject leaders of physical education should advocate for the promotion of a healthy school environment.
- Long-term engagement in professional development as part of the physical education learning journey is valued and supported (with particular reference to best practice as advocated by for example, physical education subject associations, governmental or local professional development centres or teachers' unions where membership of communities of practice is encouraged).

Suggested reading linked to the PRIME PETE Vision for Student Teacher Health and Wellbeing

1. Hascher, T. and Waber, J. (2021). Teacher Well-Being: A Systematic Review of the Research Literature from the Year 2000–2019. *Educational Research Review* 34
2. O'Brien, M. (2021). The care/justice relation in teachers' and students' well-being in T. R. N. Murphy and P. Mannix-McNamara (eds.) *International Perspectives on Teacher Well-Being and Diversity*. Singapore: Springer
3. Do schools kill creativity? Sir Ken Robinson <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iG9CE55wbtY>
4. Why schools need to embrace kids' creativity | Sir Ken Robinson <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=g4IAa8wZlqU>
5. Thorburn, M. (Ed.). (2017). *Wellbeing, Education and Contemporary Schooling*. London: Routledge.

7. Finalising the PRIME PETE modules and micro-modules

The final part of the module and micro-module development involved looking closely at the work of IO#3.

In summary, the project partners had debated the *core* statements drawn from the teacher profile (PPETP IO#3). The initial five dimensions with the top thirteen statements identified from the Delphi study (IO#1) and embedded in the proposed PPETP (IO#3) were deemed to be too limiting. It was agreed that the *core* statements should be further expanded to include additional statements from the *extended* statements (IO#3). Therefore, seventeen further statements (drawn from the extended statements) were added to the *core* statements. This resulted in thirty *core* statements which were agreed as representing a *minimum* competency for a teacher of primary PE, while the addition of thirty-six extended statements represented the full spectrum of 66 competencies. These sixty-six competencies represent the *higher yet achievable expectations* for students related both to the amount of time dedicated to the programmes they experience as well as their own personal capacity.

This examination of the work from IO#3 prompted the refining of the coding process (IO#5). An excel sheet with the sixty-six statements/competences of the PPETP was prepared for all partners to facilitate the recoding of the modules and micro-modules using a YES/NO check box (green = YES, pink = NO). This was the first time the partners had a complete overview of the PRIME PETE capacity to meet the dimensions and statements and to identify if there were ‘gaps’, i.e., where dimensions and/or statements were not being met, and therefore additional modules could be required. ‘Gaps’ were defined as statements with fewer than four occurrences (see Appendix 6).

Six additional modules were developed (see Table 7). In addition to the module development described above, three further overarching elements (OE) were identified. Firstly, as described above, an element of self-reflection on aspects of learning and teaching of PE was identified as important for primary teachers of PE (informed by the recommendations of LTT 2 Brixen and IO#2) hence the OE: *the Teacher as a Reflective Practitioner in Physical Education*. Two additional overarching elements were also developed: *Research in Physical Education* (10 ECTS) and the *Professional Placement in Physical Education* (20% of the PRIME PETE Programme). A framework for both elements is outlined to support the bespoke development of these elements by individual HEIs. These OEs were developed in response to the gaps identified during the refining of the coding process. In summary, the PRIME PETE programme consists of thirteen module exemplars, fourteen micro-module exemplars and three overarching elements (see Table 8). Table 9 shows the PRIME PETE programme illustrating an overview of the coding process, showing the dimensions only, due to space restrictions for a table of this size. The expanded version with further detail

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related to the 5 dimensions and 66 statements is available on the PRIME PETE website. This PRIME PETE excel sheet can be used as a useful *checklist* (guide) for any module development.

The PRIME PETE programme has endeavoured to meet the competencies outlined in the PPETP. Nevertheless, some gaps remain. This refining of the coding clearly illustrates the successes and limitations of the PRIME PETE programme in meeting the breadth of the five dimensions and 66 statements. Given the time constraints on the project it was not possible to extend the work of IO#5 any further.

Table 7: Six additional PRIME PETE modules

Learning to Move in Water in Physical Education
Inclusive Primary Physical Education
Pedagogical Project in Physical Education
Theory and Practice of Physical Education
Development and Implementation of Extra Curricular Activities
Subject Leadership in Physical Education

The PRIME PETE module and micro-module template required further editing to reflect the coding process discussed above with reference to the design of the template - one row (white) of the template would show any codes from the 30 core statements (Dimensions Core) and the next row (green) would contain any of the codes for the extended 36 statements (Dimensions Extended). This is reflected in Table 1 above the PRIME PETE template.

Having recoded their modules and micro-modules using the PRIME PETE checklist the partners recorded the outcomes of this process on the revised PRIME PETE template for each module and micro-module. All the PRIME PETE modules and micro-modules can be viewed on the 'Teaching Modules' tab on the PRIME PETE website.

Table 8: PRIME PETE modules (M), micro-modules (MM) and Overarching Elements (OE)

Module (M) and Micro Module (MM) and Overarching Elements (OE)	Element
Planning and Implementation of Physical Education	M
Planning and Implementation of Physical Education: Child-appropriate Physical Education	MM
Active School Models	M
Active School Models: Active School	MM
Understanding Physical Education	M
Understanding Physical Education: Cooperative Challenges Outdoors	MM
Understanding Physical Education: Creative Dance	MM
Understanding Physical Education: Fundamental Movement Skills	MM
Foundations of Primary Physical Education	M
Foundations of Physical Education: Knowledge and Understanding of Physical Activity Recommendations	MM
Foundations of Physical Education: Motivation, Motivational Climate and Enjoyment in Physical Education	MM
Foundations of Physical Education: Values-based Education through Sport and Physical Education	MM
Didactics of Physical Education	M
Didactics of Physical Education: Communication and Interaction	MM
Didactics of Physical Education: Organisation and Classroom Management	MM
School Physical and Health Education	M
School Physical and Health Education: Inclusive Primary Physical Education	MM
School Physical and Health Education: Swimming as a Tool to Support Lifelong Physical Activity	MM
Teaching Physical Education	M
Teaching Physical Education: Motor Development, Learning and Implications for Teaching	MM
Teaching Physical Education: Classroom Management	MM
Learning to Move in Water in Physical Education	M
Inclusive Primary Physical Education	M
Pedagogical Project in Physical Education	M
Theory and Practice of Physical Education	M
Development and Implementation of Extra Curricular Activities	M
Subject Leadership in Physical Education	M
Professional Placement in Physical Education	OE
The Teacher as a Reflective Practitioner in Physical Education	OE
Research in Physical Education	OE

Table 9: The PRIME PETE Modules, Micro-modules and Overarching Elements illustrating an overview of the coding process

Module (M) and Micro Module (MM) and Overarching Elements (OE)	Element	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5
Planning and Implementation of Physical Education	M	no	yes	no	no	no
Planning and Implementation of Physical Education: Child-appropriate Physical Education	MM	no	yes	no	no	no
Active School Models	M	no	no	no	yes	yes
Active School Models: Active School	MM	no	no	no	yes	yes
Understanding Physical Education	M	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Understanding Physical Education: Cooperative Challenges Outdoors	MM	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Understanding Physical Education: Creative Dance	MM	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Understanding Physical Education: Fundamental Movement Skills	MM	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Foundations of Primary Physical Education	M	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Foundations of Physical Education: Knowledge and Understanding of Physical Activity Recommendations	MM	yes	no	yes	no	no
Foundations of Physical Education: Motivation, Motivational Climate and Enjoyment in Physical Education	MM	no	no	yes	no	no
Foundations of Physical Education: Values-based Education through Sport and Physical Education	MM	no	no	no	yes	no
Didactics of Physical Education	M	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Didactics of Physical Education: Communication and Interaction	MM	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Didactics of Physical Education: Organisation and Classroom Management	MM	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
School Physical and Health Education	M	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
School Physical and Health Education: Inclusive Primary Physical Education	MM	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
School Physical and Health Education: Swimming as a Tool to Support Lifelong Physical Activity	MM	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Teaching Physical Education	M	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Teaching Physical Education: Motor Development, Learning and Implications for Teaching	MM	yes	yes	no	no	no
Teaching Physical Education: Classroom Management	MM	no	yes	no	no	no
Learning to Move in Water in Physical Education	M	yes	yes	no	no	no
Inclusive Primary Physical Education	M	yes	yes	yes	yes	no
Pedagogical Project in Physical Education	M	yes	no	no	no	yes
Theory and Practice of Physical Education	M	yes	yes	no	yes	no
Development and Implementation of Extra Curricular Activities	M	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Subject Leadership in Physical Education	M	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Professional Placement in Physical Education	OE	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
The Teacher as a Reflective Practitioner in Physical Education	OE	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Research in Physical Education	OE	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes

Dimension 1: Knowledge Development and Management, **Dimension 2:** Teaching, Learning and Assessment, **Dimension 3:** Learner Empowerment, Potential, Diversity and Creativity, **Dimension 4:** Values, Social Leadership and Communication, **Dimension 5:** Development as Reflective Professionals and Life-Long Learners

8. Conclusions

The PRIME PETE mission (IO#4) presents the overall vision for the PRIME PETE programme. The PRIME PETE suite of modules, micro-modules and overarching elements (IO#5) is now available on the PRIME PETE website. It

- is the first European teacher education programme for primary physical education available online. (Other possible platforms for sharing the PRIME PETE programme are the Erasmus+ results platform, researchgate.net, as well as zenodo.org, allowing assignment of a Doi-number to the publication).
- may be used by target groups to support the development of teacher education programmes with a focus on teaching of primary physical education.
- provides flexibility for programme design using a modular approach.
- can be implemented using blended or face to face delivery.
- can facilitate student and staff mobility between universities across Europe.
- can inform professional development in undergraduate, postgraduate and in-service settings.

Further development of physical education programmes for primary teachers by any HEI's can be informed by IO#5 as well as the other outputs from the PRIME PETE project.

9. References

Attach, P. (2022). What is the European Credit Transfer System (ECTS)? Retrieved 4 May 2023, from <https://www.study.eu/article/what-is-the-ects-european-credit-transfer-and-accumulation-system>.

CALOHEE (n.d.). CALOHEE. Retrieved 5 May 2023, from <https://www.calohee.eu/>

ECTS User's Guide (2015). Retrieved 4 May 2023, from <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/da7467e6-8450-11e5-b8b7-01aa75ed71a1>.

Historica Canada Education Portal. (n.d.). Retrieved 4 May 2023, from <http://education.historicacanada.ca/en/tools?theme=5>.

Tuning Educational Structures in Europe (2018). Retrieved 4 May 2023 from <https://www.calohee.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/1.2-Guidelines-and-Reference-Points-for-the-Design-and-Delivery-of-Degree-Programmes-in-Teacher-Education-FINAL-v2.pdf>

Appendices

Appendix 1: Glossary Specific to IO#5

Codes/Coding a system of yes/no check words used to establish if modules and micro-module meet the PRIME PETE profile statements/competencies.

Competence the ability to do something successfully or efficiently. Competences are defined in the PRIME PETE teacher profile. They are defined as a combination of knowledge, skills and attitudes, where:

- knowledge is composed of the facts and figures, concepts, ideas and theories which are already established or constructed from the practice and support the understanding of a certain area or subject.
- skills are defined as the ability and capacity to carry out processes and use the existing knowledge to achieve results.
- attitudes describe the disposition and mind-sets to act or react to ideas, persons or situations.

Dimensions are an aspect or feature of a competency (Tuning CALOHEE, 2018 p.2)

Elements are the essential or characteristic parts of the PRIME PETE programme

European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS) the Europe-wide use of the student workload based ECTS not only allows student mobility across Europe and in other countries as well; it can also facilitate programme design and development, particularly with respect to coordinating and rationalising the demands made on students by concurrent course units. In other words, ECTS permits us to plan how best to use students' time to achieve the aims of the educational process, rather than considering teachers' time as the primary constraint and students' time as basically limitless.

Learning Outcomes are what a learner is expected to know, understand and/or be able to do at the end of a period of learning. Learning outcomes are typically characterised using active verbs expressing knowledge, comprehension, application, analysis; These are identified for each module and micro-module of the PRIME PETE programme.

Lecture an educational talk to an audience, especially one of a large group of students in a university. This term is used in each module of the PRIME PETE programme.

Learning Teaching and Training (LTT) Event in an Erasmus + Project.

Micro Module (MM) is a part/fraction of a module to help students have a specific understanding of a particular topic in a module.

Module is a distinct, discrete, self-contained element of the PRIME PETE programme. A module is a self-contained, formally structured learning experience. It has a coherent and explicit set of learning outcomes, expressed in terms of competences to be obtained, and appropriate assessment criteria.

Modular primary PETE programme

Movement Based (MB) is a lesson/workshop/seminar/studio/laboratory-based session that is face to face and practical, where the key focus is on learning through movement/physical activity as the method of delivery.

Offline Delivery is an educational class that is recorded and available for students at an exact time or for an exact time-period. Students can view a recording, sometimes referred to as a 'lecture capture,' in their own time as long as they have access to internet.

Online Delivery refers to a lecture delivered virtually as opposed to in-person. Online lectures may be asynchronous, in that students can watch a lecture at a preferred time and at their own pace. Other online lectures may be synchronous, where students must be present at a specified time to view the lecture in real-time.

Open Course Platform is a free online access platform that hosts courses of study that may be accessed by many people over the internet. The PRIME PETE website hosts the PRIME PETE programmes.

Overarching Element (OE) in the PRIME PETE programme may be a module or a piece of work or process that may be woven into many modules and micro-modules e.g., reflection, research project, school placement.

Professional Placement: see School Placement.

Programme refers to an organised sequence of teaching and learning experiences.

School Placement is formally examined university professional placement where students are placed to teach physical education and where some may teach other subjects.

School Placement Tutor is a person who supports and mentors student teachers and evaluates their practice while on placement preferably with physical education subject expertise.

Seminar/Workshop/Tutorial students participate in a small group setting with supervisor and/or peers.

Setting refers to the mode(s) of delivery e.g., Online, hybrid, offline, movement based, theory based.

Short Description are words or expressions used to describe or identify modules.

Structured Independent Work Engagement with specified readings and resources to support research or assignments.

Themes are important ideas or topics that underpin the PRIME PETE programme e.g., digital learning, inclusion.

Theory Based (TB) is a lecture-based instructional approach. It refers to a traditional classroom teaching model, where the instructor delivers a lecture verbally using tools such as a projector, visual display surface and writing surface (e.g., a chalkboard, dry-erase whiteboard or whiteboard).

Tutorial: see Seminar.

Universal Design for Learning (UDL) is an educational framework with three key principles: engagement, representation, and action and expression. It supports accessibility for all in the design and implementation of the PETE programme.

Modular primary PETE programme

Workload is a learner-oriented quantitative measure of the learning activities that may feasibly be required for the achievement of the learning outcomes. Workload comprises the estimated time which is needed for any type of learning: lectures, seminars, practical work, private study, information retrieval, research, group work, independent studies, examinations, etc. The concept of workload is also the basis for allocating credits within a credit system such as the ECTS and is used within the PRIME PETE programme in an indicative manner.

Workshop: see Seminar.

Appendix 2: Learning Teaching and Training 2 Brixen-Bressanone Programme

PRIME PETE PROJECT LTT IN BRIXEN-BRESSANONE 6-11 JUNE 2022 PROGRAMME		
Bring with you:	<i>Paper and a pen (for theoretical activities)</i> <i>Clothes and shoes for exercising and hiking (for practical activities)</i>	
Monday 6th June		
9.00-11.00 A.M.	Introductory activities Profs Susan Marron & Frances Murphy (Dublin City University)	Hostel, "Sala Teatro"
11.00 A.M.-12.00 P.M.	Foundations of a child-appropriate Physical Education (Theoretical) Prof Claude Scheuer (University of Luxembourg)	Hostel, "Sala Teatro"
14.00-16.00	Walk in the old town and surroundings	Brixen
Tuesday 7th June		
9.00-11.00 A.M.	Physical Education through dance (creative) – (Practical) Profs Susan Marron & Frances Murphy (Dublin City University)	Sportzone South Brixen, Via del Laghetto / Fischzuchtweg
11.00 A.M.-12.00 P.M.	Didactics of PE with a focus on communication and interaction (Practical) Prof. Francis Ries (University of Seville)	Sportzone South Brixen, Via del Laghetto / Fischzuchtweg
14.00-16.00	Didactics of PE with a focus on communication and interaction (Theoretical) Prof. Francis Ries (University of Seville)	University, Room A 1.60
16.00-17.00	Students' meeting	University, Room A 1.60
Wednesday 8th June		
9.00 A.M.-16.00	Hiking (with lunch box)	(TBD)
Thursday 9th June		
9.00 A.M.-12.00 P.M.	Values-based education through sport and PE (Theoretical and practical) Prof Attilio Carraro (University of Bozen-Bolzano)	University, Room A 1.60
14.00-15.00	Teaching PE (with simulated teaching) – (Theoretical) Prof Marcos Onofre (University of Lisbon)	University, Room A 1.60
15.00-17.00	Teaching PE (with simulated teaching) – (Practical) Prof Marcos Onofre (University of Lisbon)	University, Room A -1.60
Friday 10th June		
9.00-10.30 A.M.	Inclusive primary PE and its implementation (Theoretical) Prof Dana Masaryková (Tmava University)	University, Room A 1.60
10.30 A.M.-12.00 P.M.	Inclusive primary PE and its implementation (Practical) Prof Dana Masaryková (Tmava University)	University, Room A -1.60
14.00-15.45	Foundations of a child-appropriate Physical Education (Theoretical) Prof Claude Scheuer (University of Luxembourg)	IFO school gym, Via Montessori / Montessori- Straße
16.00-17.00	Students' meeting	University, Room A 1.06
For further information Please, email giampaolo.santi@unibz.it		

Appendix 3: Micro-modules (MM) implemented at the Brixen LTT event

Dimension 1	Dimension 2	Dimension 3	Dimension 4	Dimension 5
<p>D1K1 Advanced knowledge and understanding of the development of fundamental movement skills.</p> <p>MM1 Physical Education through Dance (creative)</p> <p>MM1 Communication and Interaction during PE classes</p> <p>MM1 Physical Education through Cooperative Challenges Outdoors</p>	<p>D2S1 Ability to plan and teach quality physical education lessons.</p> <p>MM1 - Teaching PE – Classroom Management</p> <p>MM1 -Physical Education through Dance (creative)</p> <p>MM1 - Inclusive primary physical education and its implementation</p> <p>MM1 Communication and Interaction during PE classes</p> <p>MM1 - Physical Education through Cooperative Challenges Outdoors</p> <p>MM1 -Foundations of a child-appropriate physical education</p>	<p>D3C1 Capacity and commitment to support the learning and development of all students regardless of their ability levels.</p> <p>MM1 Physical Education through Dance (creative)</p> <p>MM1 - Inclusive primary physical education and its implementation</p> <p>MM1 Physical Education through Cooperative Challenges Outdoors</p> <p>MM1 Foundations of a child-appropriate physical education</p>	<p>D4C1 Capacity and commitment to the healthy development of primary school students</p> <p>MM1 Inclusive primary physical education and its implementation</p> <p>MM1 Communication and Interaction during PE classes</p> <p>MM1 Physical Education through Cooperative Challenges Outdoors</p> <p>MM1 Foundations of Primary Physical Education: Values-based education through sport and PE</p>	<p>D5C1 Capacity and commitment to actively advocate for physical education in the school and beyond</p>

Dimension 1	Dimension 2	Dimension 3	Dimension 4	Dimension 5
<p>D1K2 Knowledge about children’s overall development</p> <p>MM1 Communication and Interaction during PE classes</p>	<p>D2S2 Ability to provide a positive and safe learning environment.</p> <p>MM1 Teaching PE – Classroom Management</p> <p>MM1 Physical Education through Dance (creative)</p> <p>MM1 Inclusive primary physical education and its implementation</p> <p>MM1 - Communication and Interaction during PE classes</p> <p>MM1 Foundations of a child-appropriate physical education</p> <p>MM1 Physical Education through Cooperative Challenges Outdoors</p>	<p>D3C2 Capacity and commitment to motivate, inspire learners and support their empowerment.</p> <p>MM1 Physical Education through Dance (creative)</p> <p>MM1 -Inclusive primary physical education and its implementation</p> <p>MM1 Foundations of a child-appropriate physical education</p> <p>MM1 Physical Education through Cooperative Challenges Outdoors</p>	<p>D4S1 Ability to communicate effectively both verbally and non-verbally.</p> <p>MM1 Physical Education through Dance (creative)</p> <p>MM1 Communication and Interaction during PE classes</p> <p>MM1 Foundations of a child-appropriate physical education</p> <p>MM1 Foundations of Primary Physical Education: Values-based education through sport and PE</p>	

Dimension 1	Dimension 2	Dimension 3	Dimension 4	Dimension 5
<p>D1K3 Knowledge of physical activity recommendations for children and young people</p> <p>MM1 Communication and Interaction during PE classes</p>	<p>D2S3 Ability to plan long-term and short-term physical education programmes based on students’ developmental level and readiness.</p> <p>MM1 Physical Education through Dance (creative)</p> <p>MM1 Communication and Interaction during PE classes</p> <p>MM1 Foundations of a child-appropriate physical education</p> <p>MM1 Physical Education through Cooperative Challenges Outdoors</p>	<p>D3C3 Capacity and commitment to create situations and climates in which learners increase their self-esteem and confidence.</p> <p>MM1 Physical Education through Dance (creative)</p> <p>MM1 Inclusive primary physical education and its implementation</p> <p>MM1 Foundations of a child-appropriate physical education</p> <p>MM1 Physical Education through Cooperative Challenges Outdoors</p>	<p>D4S2 Ability to promote ethical behaviour in learners and foster a culture of valuing diversity within the classroom setting diversity.</p> <p>MM1 Communication and Interaction during PE classes</p> <p>MM1 Foundations of a child-appropriate physical education</p> <p>MM1 Foundations of Primary Physical Education: Values-based education through sport and PE</p>	

Appendix 4: Ethical Practice Using Personal iPhones in the PRIME PETE Learning Teaching and Training Event Programme

Ethical Practice Using Personal iPhones in the PRIME PETE Learning Teaching and Training Event Programme

Lisbon, Portugal 12th -16th September 2022

The PRIME PETE Partners and their Universities and Organisations fully respects your right as a student and our right as lecturers to privacy. Together we actively seek to preserve the privacy rights of those who share information with us. Any personal information which you volunteer will be treated with the highest standards of security and confidentiality by all in attendance at the PRIME PETE Learning Teaching and Training Event. We will endeavour to ensure the highest standards of security and confidentiality everyone participating the PRIME PETE Learning Teaching and Training Event. All parties are expected to use mobile devices in accordance with their University Policies and practices.

The purpose of using mobile devices in the LTT Lisbon is to use the personal mobile technology to self and peer assess your movement of tasks and activities in the Micro Module 2 Promoting Fundamental Movement Skills in All Children. during the Prime Pete LTT Lisbon. With this in mind here are our boundaries we expect for the best way to ensure online safety using personal mobile devices for this event:

- Respect people's privacy.
- Be kind. Respect is key. We should not do anything that you know you would be unhappy with, such as forwarding material that would hurt or embarrass someone else. Please do not post any material used in the module(s) to any social platform.
- Think about the future. It's an important lesson to learn that online material is forever.
- You must delete the film clips before leaving the gym/sports hall/classroom.
- Communicate your concerns to partner(s) if you have any concerns.

Thank you for your understanding, PRIME PETE Partners

Appendix 5: Learning Teaching and Training 3 University of Lisbon, Portugal Programme

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

LTT 4 & 5
Lisbon , 12-16 September 2022
Hosted by Faculty of Human Kinetics, University of Lisbon
Estádio Universitário de Lisboa
Programme

Sunday, 11 th September

20.00h - *Dinner (organizer: Marcos, Restaurant Sabor Mineiro, Av. José Malhoa, 16D)*

Monday 12th September (Responsibles: António e Marcos, all day)

9.30h-10.30h: Introduction to the LTT 4 & 5 – Claude Scheuer (via on-line), Sport Medicine Centre Auditorium

10.30h-12.30h: Promoting Fundamental Movement Skills in All Children – Susan Marron, Sports Hall 1

12:30h-14:00h: Lunch Break (Organizers: António e Marcos, EUL restaurant)

14:00h-15:00h: Micro Module from UTrvana, Dana Masarykova & Jana Labudova, Sport Medicine Centre Auditorium

15:00h-16:00h: Micro Module from UTrvana (tbd), Dana Masarykova & Jana Labudova, Sports Hall 1

20.00h - Dinner (Organizers: Nuno e António, place tbi)

Tuesday 13th September (Responsibles: Nuno and António: morning, João: all day)

9.30h-12.30h: Knowledge and understanding of physical activity recommendations Attilio Carraro & Giampaolo Santi, Sport Medicine Centre Auditorium

12:30h-14:00h: Lunch Break (Organizers: Nuno, António, EUL restaurant)

14:00h-15:00h: Organization and management of PE classes, Francis Ries, Sport Medicine Centre Auditorium

15:00-16:00h: Organization and management of PE classes, Francis Ries, Sports Hall 1

20.00h - Dinner (free)

Wednesday 14th September

Social activity & place TBD (morning)

12:30h-14:00h: Lunch Break (Organizers: João, António)

Free Afternoon and dinner

Thursday 15th September (Responsibles: Nuno and Marcos: all day, António: morning)

9.30-12.30: Teaching PE – Particularities of the Motor Development and Learning of children between 3 and 10 years old and their implications for the Teaching and Learning of PE – Nuno Ferro, Carolina Santos, Sara Martins e Diogo Ribeiro, Sports Hall 1

12:30h-14:00h: Lunch Break (Organizers: Nuno, Marcos, EUL restaurant)

14:00h-16:00h: EUPEA presentation, Rose-Marie Repond (via on-line), Sport Medicine Centre Auditorium

20.00h - Dinner (Organizers: Marcos, Nuno, place tbd)

Friday 16th September (Marcos: all day, António: morning, João and Nuno: afternoon)

9.30-12.30 Micro Module from ULux (tbd), Claude Scheuer, Sport Medicine Centre Auditorium

12:30h-14:00h: Lunch Break (António, João, Marcos e Nuno, EUL restaurant)

14:00h-15:00h: Closure of the LTT 4&5 – Claude Scheuer, Sport Medicine Centre Auditorium

Free Dinner

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Appendix 6: Meeting the Dimensions and Statements: Gaps

<i>Sub Dimension</i>	<i>Frequency of Occurrence</i>	<i>Statement</i>
D1K7	0	D1K7 Advanced knowledge and critical understanding of sociological, philosophical, psychological and pedagogical theories in education and physical education
D1S3	3	D1S3 Ability to use evidence-based educational theories and practices and ignore pseudoscientific claims and programmes.
D1C4	3	D1C4 Capacity and commitment to critically reflect on educational policies.
D2K4	1	D2K4 Advanced knowledge and understanding of different motor learning theories, and typical and atypical motor development, and practical consequences.
D2S5	4	D2S5 Ability to using digital technology for learning and assessment
D3K4	4	D3K4 Advanced knowledge of school counselling processes and of how to advise students (and their families/guardians) to develop learners' resources.
D4S3	2	D4S3 Ability to reflect on personal capacity, qualities and competencies as a subject leader in physical education.
D4S5	2	D4S5 Ability to organise extracurricular activities, and other educational events in response to social need
D5S2	1	D5S2 Ability to develop adequate coping strategies, social support or preventive identification and influencing of stressors in the private and professional context.